

POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES BASED ON CNT BUCKYPAPERS

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SUMMARY

Work is focused on the fabrication of carbon nanotube thin sheets – buckypapers and their nanocomposites. Firstly, buckypapers are produced by a filtration of a well-dispersed nanotube solution. Subsequently, porous buckypapers are impregnated by epoxy based resin by two different processing techniques. Prepared high-volume fraction carbon nanotube composites were tested for mechanical and electrical properties.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotube, Nanocomposite, Mechanical properties, Electrical properties, Buckypaper

ABSTRACT

Buckypapers are thin sheets of entangled carbon nanotubes (CNTs), which are highly porous meshes. They can be prepared by vacuum filtration of well-dispersed CNT solution or compression method. Final properties of buckypapers can be affected with various factors, such as concentration of CNT solution, sonication time, vacuum pressure, solvent, nature of nanotubes or surface functionalization by polymers¹. This work is a continuation of our previous work regarding the effect of chemical oxidation on structural integrity of multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) with reagents of different oxidation power². Buckypapers from MWCNTs oxidised by acids hydrochloric acid, piranha, nitric acid (HNO₃), permanganate and base ammonia were prepared. The effect of different oxidation treatment of MWCNTs on mechanical properties, surface conductivity and porosity of buckypapers prepared from these MWCNTs is studied. High-volume fraction CNT nanocomposites were prepared from these buckypapers. The effect of different procedure conditions and oxidation treatment of MWCNTs on mechanical properties and conductivity of composites was studied. The prepared composites exhibit improved mechanical and electrical properties.

Buckypaper production and its properties

Dry buckypapers prepared by vacuum filtration of well-dispersed CNT - water solution were uniform, smooth and crack-free disks exhibiting significant structural integrity.

Homogeneous and dense morphology is achieved not only on the surface but also through the thickness of the buckypapers. Average pore size of intra-bundle porosity distribution was about 12 nm. The highest conductivity is reached for HNO₃ treated films (surface conductivity ~ 18 S/cm). The latter also exhibited relatively high mechanical behaviour under tensile loading (Young's modulus ~ 1.2 GPa, stress at break ~ 3.9 MPa).

High-volume fraction CNT composites from buckypaper

High-volume fraction CNT composites were produced by two different techniques – autoclave resin film infusion (RFI) or simply soaking with resin solution. In both cases impregnation of CNT network with polymer was observed. The volume fraction of nanofiller in final epoxy-CNT nanocomposites were dependent on different processing conditions (concentration of epoxy resin solution, temperature, pressure) and also on oxidative treatment of CNTs. The final mechanical or electrical properties of nanocomposites could be modified and tuned by oxidation of CNTs and processing conditions. Some of prepared buckypapers composites showed significant improved electrical and mechanical properties (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Comparison mechanical properties of neat buckypaper, neat resin and buckypaper composite.

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